

The Dimensions of Holistic Personality Development in Contemporary Society

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ABSTRACT: The holistic development of a society implies the holistic development of the individual. Both the dialectical term “development” and its transfer over the entire duration of life prove to be favorable of researching holistic personality development. The direction of development or the description of its content is dependent on the cultural–ideological context; the image regarding the human being and the moral values that underscore the concept. Yet despite cultural boundaries, various sizes and areas of personality development can be established and differentiated. On the other hand, a general meta–criterion can be formulated in setting the goal of personal development—often expressed by concepts like “mature personality” or “personality stable.” Thus, the active holistic support for the development of human personality proves to be an urgent need in the complex context of contemporary society.

KEY WORDS: development, personality, holistic dimensions, target development, contemporary society

Because a society is composed of individuals, a holistic development of society automatically implies a holistic development of its individuals. This can be seen from several perspectives. This article proposes a debate on the characteristics of individual personality development from a psychological perspective, namely to what extent the idea of holism is applicable in this context and if it is possible to formulate a uniform concept. In the current postmodern society, when consciously planned personal development is seen

as an individual task, it requires a reflection of differential criteria that underlie it.

The Context of the “Personality Development” Concept

Already this concept composed by double term contains a lot of different directions and meanings, which are found in part in different but related scientific disciplines. What does human development actually mean? The current development psychology starts from the premise of a *dialectical* development model, where the outside world influences the individual which in turn has an active impact on the environment. This model also postulates—unlike the traditional mechanistic model—the existence of an individual who actively participates and acts in its own development process.¹ The *mechanistic* model is contrary unidirectional and starts from the premise that the development of the interior capacities unfolds irreversibly, according to an interior pattern.²

Besides the extension of the term of *development* from a passive role to an active one of the individual, there are modern approaches that extend the term of *development* from childhood and youth to the entire range of life, from the overall development domain of special areas of development or from a standard development of the development of special groups (gifted, disabled, delinquents, etc.). Meanwhile stands the discussion transfer of the development towards maturity in favor of sustainable development—meaning both gains and losses.³ Thus the *personality development* involves, according to Staudinger “irreversible transformations age-dependent in solving ability but also complicity in contexts of development.”⁴ This has to do with “intra-individual transformations relatively sustainable over time related to living and behavior.”⁵

The term *development* is often used in a positive sense as “growth”, when referring to the interaction between biological conditions and environmental influences.⁶ In every phase of life it is possible a gain of new knowledge. Meanwhile development involves a selective optimization or “specialization”, meaning not only gains but also losses due to a conscious or unconscious surrender to

certain options.⁷ On the one hand the trend toward perfection, to maximum achievements indeed produced high performance in art, technical, science and other fields of culture, but not any higher level can be defined as progress. Some optimization or maximization targets can quickly collide with the criteria of justice, fair play or with one of a “good life.”⁸

According to Ulich D. *personality development* means a steady transformation, adapted to the age in one “positive” direction, which includes the center of self. So in this context developing involves a holistic understanding of the individual and the values found in the legal context of personal and society’s expectations.⁹ Both the image of man and moral evaluation as well as the cultural and ideological framework, namely the image about what is best, highest or most desirable in development, influences the direction of the development.¹⁰ Because not everything that can be realized is also desirable, beneficial or allowed, the issue of the rules and values in question intervenes. Added to them are also different expectations or concepts of a good life. It is noticed that not only wishes adapt to the possibilities but also the other way around: certain desires have a motivating effect in widening the space of possibilities.¹¹

The term “*personality*” is the sum of human forms of living and behavior, their internal interdependence as well as to external factors. This is not about the specific behavior in a particular situation or mood changes, but more about the center of each individual.¹² To it belong behavioral habits, dispositional qualities, environmental influences, own bio-psychological and emotional concepts as well as cognitive - psychological characteristics.¹³

Regarding the *description* of human personality there are different paths in psychology. On the one hand, it is regarded as a core as a stable part of the individual which leads to the formation and framing in some types - such as the theory of temperaments or “basic forms of fear.”¹⁴ On the other hand there is the possibility of looking at an individual not in the categories but “like a mosaic of lots of features” based on several *dimensions*. In this tradition was Eysenck, then the concept of the “Big Five”¹⁵ or the concept of Gray (1990). Terms like e.g.: subjectivity, interaction, personality as structure or process, such as temporal causality represent concepts that allow

an emphasis of the individual specific of the human personality.¹⁶ In addition Cloninger's concept deserves to be remembered, which is based on both primary-genetic structures (four dimensions of temperament) as well as structures formed through socialization (three dimensions of character).¹⁷

It becomes obvious that genetics and culture - both aspects contribute to the development of the human personality and influence each other. Personal, biological and institutional factors interfere throughout life, "development tasks" are dependent on age and personal maturity, and together create a "biography script of life,"¹⁸ which in turn further influences the individual development and the practice of individual socialization.¹⁹ On the other hand biographical patterns are precisely the result of such formative factors, which in turn influence the perception of a good life and its implementation, involving the experience of failure. Both external factors e.g.: social structures and premises, institutional or causal, and the interior—such as our own wishes and beliefs—are partly unpredictable.²⁰

The Dimensions of the Development of Human Personality

The notion of "*personality*" not only defines but limits the dimensions of development. Thus changes are differentiated in cognitive issues (perceptual, structure of thought, ability to concentrate, attitudes, etc.), motivational, emotional (feelings, value and personal effectiveness, emotion regulation, etc.) as well as social. At the same time changes are defined of the abilities belonging to them both over the age as well as in the context of social changes and personal resources.²¹

In addition there's a difference between *qualitative changes*—when *something else* is added and something is replaced or disappears—and *quantitative changes*, when there is an increase or decrease of "the same way."²² In developmental psychology today is considered that both types of changes occur. Since the *mechanistic concept* sees the individual as a complex machine, it emphasizes quantitative development, while the *organismic concept*, due to

underlining elements of self-organization, emphasizes more the qualitative changes.²³

The concepts “personal maturity” and “wisdom”—marking the direction of personality development—have been rediscovered and partly engaged in empirical studies lately.²⁴ The question, if these concepts are valid targets or directions of development, and if so, in what defining context. The image of man and ethical philosophical concepts that underlie them plays an important role in this regard.

The term used here of *mature stable personality* differs both from the image of man of the organismic concept and to the adaptivity term. Thus the difference between maturity and adaptivity lies in their motivation.²⁵ By adaptivity is meant the optimal mental functioning, which manifests itself in a state of gratitude.²⁶ A *mature personality* exceeds however the level of adaptivity and contains an additional aspect of value. It thus includes certain attitudes, values and patterns of behavior that do not have only a functional character. Personality maturity is measured by balancing the interests of self and others. Consideration for others does not have an adaptive character, but is understood as the principle that consideration for others is manifested in Kantian²⁷ imperative sense and not in the interest of its own advantages.²⁸

The psychological difference between the concept of maturity as adaptivity and the concept of maturity as value aspect was born based on two philosophical conceptions about happiness in antiquity: *Hedonia and Eudaimonia*.²⁹ Philosophy was the first to show interest in factors that lead to a successful life and that in consequence formulated normative rules in ancient times, sayings, concepts of wisdom or happiness. The philosophical concept of happiness *Hedonia* comes from Aristippos of Kyrene and builds on adaptivity and wellbeing, which is expressed by positive feelings, personal satisfaction, internal control and extraversion.³⁰ The concept of *Eudaimonia* implies in philosophical context a positive development in life and self-fulfillment. It comes from the famous Aristotle and realized by developing the maximum development of own potential and qualities. Ryff (1989) defines *Eudaimonia* as a combination of self-acceptance, personal development, interpersonal relationships, autonomy, life targets in daily activity. Here it is important to act not

to receive appreciation, but out of principle. Well-being is thus not the product but the process of personal fulfillment.³¹

In principle both concepts (adaptivity / *Hedonia* and maturity / *Eudaimonia*) are regarded as “gains” in development. Yet there are overlaps, because a mature behavior may at least in part have an adaptive character too. On the other hand not all hedonistic joy is based on an eudaimonist cause. One can thus understand why certain changes in life that cause non-adaptive reactions may eventually lead to maturity yet.³²

Because a *mature personality* represents a variable cultural concept,³³ is not based on the premise of the existence of some absolute criteria, but on only the realization of a meta-criterion: *consideration towards others*, or otherwise expressed—balance *between own and others well being*. The decision on the values and forms of expression linked to this is given to the individual itself.³⁴ So the question on what constitutes a positive development or the road to it is still the subject of ethical-philosophical debate nowadays.³⁵

According to Alensbacher studies a *strong personality* is characterized practically by: human orientation and capacity of contact, activity and attitude of joy, concern for connections, orientation towards information and conversation, desire for learning and socialization, serviceability and hospitality, tenacity and respect, capacity for reflection and change.³⁶

G. Roth concretely understands by the term of *personality forming* the continuous development of stress processing skills and tolerance of frustration. Thus emerges the image of a mature personality, which along its entire life perfects its systems of complacency or self-control, self-motivation and perception of reality as well as the qualities of empathy and attachment.³⁷

What however involves the successful development of personality, what model of development is promoted? I saw that in terms of content development there isn't common consensus in Western society. It's possible only achieving a general consensus on the ultimate goal of development, which can only be achieved if you take into account the responses in a generalized form, such as: wish fulfillment, the possibility of an activity meaningful life, safety, optimism, health, etc.³⁸

Psychology as empirical science was currently occupied more with the pathological aspects of human behavior than developing a promotable profile to reach a “good life”, a positive development. For a successful life does not merely mean the absence of disease or failure - which led in recent years to the development of a new perspective embodied in the “positive psychology” program.³⁹ However the psychological parameters (personality and temperament factors, sociodemographic factors, marital status and age factors, situation factors) present in empirical studies until now only a moderate causality towards the state of subjective contentment.⁴⁰

Personal values and attitudes each affect human behavior; they are however only partially convertible. Happiness, wellbeing and contentment do not constitute permanently sustainable elements in life, so that a successful development does not automatically mean a good feeling.⁴¹ Starting from the elements of a general consensus Brandstädter talks about a *successful personality development*, for which he formulates general criteria, which raise the chance of success, contentment and happiness, regardless of the path, the direction or development context. He believes that the biggest Eudaimonic profits come from customs and activities where Hedonistic pleasure blends with everyday usefulness and moral goodness.⁴²

First, it is the ability and willingness of personal reflection that is needed vis-à-vis the proposed targets, the self needs and interests and to their compatibility with the needs, interests and goals of others and in analyzing the fail situations. In achieving long-term targets auto regulative skills and emotional control are needed, that implies the ability to expect and to give up an immediate gain in favor of long-term gain.⁴³ In this context Korsgaard (1997) recalls the “principle of intelligence” which directs more on the unity of will and minimizing the intra- and interpersonal conflicts, than on the question of efficiency.⁴⁴

Secondly it comes to qualities that are at the basis of a framework of resources which makes it possible to overcome the critical situations in life and keeping a positive outlook about themselves and life. This includes both social skills to achieve social contacts (a friendly spirit, help, interest of knowledge and

own development), as well as personal skills in behavior towards crisis (see a positive meaning, inner peace, an attitude of calm) and concrete social support systems.⁴⁵

Third Brandtstädter brings into view the ability to provide a positive sense to less pleasant activities, identifying with personal targets, commitment to meaningful projects, the capacity to adapt between the development potential and limitations, and overcoming “optimization” problems through positive activities. All these are important premises for a successful development.⁴⁶

Finally Brandtstädter sees in the adaptive potential, the resilience in the face of problems and a sustainable good condition both the causes and the result of a successful life management. The adaptive potential enables the individual to plan an active life, but at the same time the possibility of compensation and overcoming the losses and balancing the needs and personal interests in the social community.⁴⁷

Holistic Development of Personality in Contemporary Society Final Considerations

The complexity of today’s society requires the urgent need of a holistic development of the human personality. Reaching a personal maturity and freedom of decision regarding achieving self realization also constituted the base goal of the Cultural Revolution of the 20th century. The 21st Century is however marked by contradictions: on the one hand holds many opportunities and possibilities, on the other hand however - many risks, limitations and dangers.⁴⁸

In the ongoing process of change of current society the individual is compelled to continually adapt to what is “new” and to redefine its identity. The individual lives and suffer today under the dictates of so-called freedom, the feeling of being alone responsible for his own life.⁴⁹

Qualification for a strong personality implies today the ability to cope in an ever changing world and to find and clarify a purpose and self life objectives. The individual has to create in the midst of a pluralist world abundant of meanings and values a self ideology,

which consists of a personal self concept, a concept of the world, a concept of personal values and a reflected image of society. This task is a great challenge, especially for young adults and requires a lot of personal skills along with social and material resources and a value-political framework for action.⁵⁰ But a strong personality, which has a strong self-awareness and professionalism can and must face the challenges and contradictions of the 21st / century.⁵¹

It becomes obvious that contemporary society through its structural complexity and challenges automatically imposes a holistic development of the human personality. A holistic image of the individual involves an ample vision on him, in which the size and areas of personality development are in a relationship of interdependence and are perceived as a whole.⁵²

We saw that modern psychological concepts already contain a holistic view of human personality, even if—due to pluralism—there is no promoted concrete model of its content. The *dialectical* understanding of human development—based on reciprocity between interior genetic elements and environmental action—also proves to be right for a holistic vision of human development, as well as expanding the concept of personality development over the entire lifespan.

Development of human personality takes place in a space of possibilities, in which the individual—due to external and internal factors—makes only one side. This horizon of possibilities—limited by the constitutional and cultural factors—raises the question regarding a good choice, maybe even the best in the despondent setting. So a *successful development* depends not only on the fulfillment of desires and reaching the proposed targets, but also on the attitude towards boundaries and obstacles.⁵³

The direction of development targets areas of thinking, feeling and action where there are losses, progresses or stagnations. Even if the direction of development turns out to be dependent on the cultural context there are basic criteria which condition a successful development. In this respect it is imposed still the necessity of research and psychological-empirical deepening of a “good life” criteria.

Finally, in the present society development it is about *balance* between society and the individual, between social solidarity and

self-fulfillment.⁵⁴ So the optimization process of the individual involves a continuous dispute with new options and possibilities of choice. But precisely a stable personality is ultimately defined by *swinging the balance* between personal needs and society's expectations. It can support its own perspective against the majority, but also at the same time is able to succumb its own interests and needs in favor of the group.⁵⁵

If the desire of personal development represents an individual's personal need—this surely depends on his own conception of man and self.⁵⁶ Unfortunately many people cannot translate this need in life positively.⁵⁷ According to Rattner the engine of human development is the aspiration after personal value, which needs to be anchored in the community. In this regard it proves important the fact to help reduce blockades both interior and exterior, in order to activate the continuous development impulse.⁵⁸

NOTES

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